

**LEVEL OF IMPLEMENTATION OF SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT (SWM)
IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS OF MATNOG, SORSOGON:
BASIS FOR INTENSIFIED SWM ACTION PLAN**

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Level of Implementation of Solid Waste Management (SWM) in Public Secondary Schools of Matnog, Sorsogon: Basis for Intensified SWM Action Plan

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Abstract

This study aimed to evaluate the implementation of solid waste management (SWM) in public secondary schools within the Municipality of Matnog, Sorsogon, during the school year 2021–2022. The research focused on four key aspects of SWM: waste minimization, waste segregation, waste storage and collection, and waste disposal, as perceived by students, teachers, and school administrators. Additionally, the study sought to identify significant differences in perceptions among these groups and to propose an intensified action plan based on the findings. A descriptive research design was employed, utilizing a questionnaire adapted from the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR) manual. The study involved 213 respondents, including school principals, assistant principals, head teachers, and students from four public secondary schools. Data were analyzed using weighted mean and ANOVA to determine the level of implementation and the significance of differences in perceptions among respondents. The results revealed varying levels of SWM implementation across the four domains. School administrators generally perceived the implementation as highly implemented, while teachers and students perceived it as moderately to slightly implemented. Significant differences were found between the perceptions of students, teachers, and administrators in waste minimization, storage, collection, and disposal, but not in waste segregation. The study underscores the need for an intensified SWM action plan to address the disparities in implementation and to enhance waste management practices in the schools and the broader community. These findings provide valuable insights for the Department of Education, local government units, and other stakeholders to strengthen SWM efforts in public secondary schools in Matnog.

Keywords: *Solid Waste Management (SWM), public secondary schools, intensified SWM action plan*

Introduction

One of the biggest threats today to humanity's existence is the rapid degradation of the environment. Human relationship to nature is no longer symbiotic but is becoming parasitism. The great demand to extract more natural resources to sustain the needs of growing population put our environment at risk. Despite the several laws promulgated by different countries around the world to help protect and preserve the environment still there are enormous challenges to achieve sustainable development. Michelle (2017) cited human activities that directly affect the ecosystem such as catching and selling of wildlife, illegal logging, slash-and-burn, quarrying, and even the improper disposal of garbage. These environmental abuses remain prevalent environmental concerns that need to be given much attention and long-term solution.

The United Nation Annual Report of 2019 warned that the speed of nature's deterioration is extraordinary and that necessary and immediate reorganization on technological, economic and social systems must be intensified. This nature's condition has been reflected on the article written by Kolb and Stebbins (2019) about the countries doing the least to protect the environment. Out of the fifteen countries listed, Burundi ranked one with 100% population exposed to unsafe air pollution levels and with 183.2% exposure to carbon emissions from fossil fuel and cement production between 2007 and 2017. In addition to this, Deforestation, disappearance of wetlands, and water pollution are the most tenacious environmental issues that need to be addressed seriously.

It cannot be denied that the world is in the brink of destruction due to the extensive man-made activities. The National Geographic (2021) identified the ways how humans impacted the environment; deforestation, pollution, overpopulation and burning fossil fuels. These changes activated climate change, soil erosion, poor air quality and unsafe water to drink. Concerned sectors in the government, agencies, private organizations and environmental activists think of the best solutions to this catastrophe and they recommend solid waste management as one of the steps that would help restore and preserve mother earth.

According to The World Bank published in September 23, 2019, that in 2016 cities in the world produced 2.01 billion tons of solid waste which is characterized by a significant increase in the rates of the accumulation of waste. Also, this production of waste is visualized to expand by 0.7 from 2016 volume to 3,40 billion tons in 2050 due to rapid population growth and urbanization. In this case, managing waste properly should be prioritized to build maintainable and habitable places and this undertaking will be implemented efficiently with proper management through unified, workable and supported communal effort.

In accordance to the statement presented, Sebastian (2021) enumerated five countries that produce the most waste in the world namely, Canada, Bulgaria, United States, Estonia and Finland. These places were identified by combining the special waste and regular municipal solid waste per capita produced by each country. The dilemma of producing huge bulk of waste was explained by Downs and Acevedo (2019) stating that biodegradable waste and cannot be properly recycled left overs fill oceans and landfills, worsen climate crisis, negatively impact wildlife and damage public health.

The reality of the solid waste management in the Philippines, is evident in the article written by Mawis (2019). Mawis argued that the implementation of Ecological Solid Waste Management Act (RA No. 9003) remains a discouraging task because of technical, political and financial crisis of concerned agencies and Local Government Units. This prevailing truth about solid waste management enactment would solve environmental issues because the law that embodies it mandate educational institutions, commercial and industrial establishments to participate in maintaining cleanliness of waterways like canals, roads or streets in their premises. Also, throwing, littering and dumping of waste or residual materials in public places are prohibited and so, clean and green environment will be strengthened.

The Philippine constitution of 1987 under Article II Section 16 recognized the need of the state to protect and preserve its environments and mandate the state to protect and advance the right of the people to a balance and healthful ecology in accordance with the rhythm and harmony of nature. As a response to this provision of the organic law, the state through its government promulgate several environmental laws such Republic Act (R.A.) No. 7586 (1992) known as National Integrated Protected Areas System Act which aims to protect and maintain the ecological balance and biodiversity; R.A. No. 8749 (1999) known as the Clean Air Act of 1999 which aims for the maintenance of clean air and sustainable development; R.A. No. 9147 (2001) also known as the Wild life Resources Conservation and Protection Act which aims to protect and conserve the wildlife and their ecosystem and; the R.A. No. 9003 (2001) also known as the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000 which directs the Local Government Units (LGU) to establish solid waste management boards within their areas of concerns.

In accordance to Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000, inter-agency formulated ten-year Solid Waste Management Plans and construction of Material Recovery Facilities (MRFs). In the same manner, the passage of R.A. No. 9512 (2008) also known as the National Environment Awareness and Education Act mandates the Department of Education, Commission on Higher Education, DENR and other concerned agencies to integrate environmental education in its school curriculum both in private and public schools. As a response, the Department of Education issued Department Order (D.O.) 52 series of 2011 providing the way to encourage school administrators, school officials and teachers to use diverse instructional materials that will help develop awareness among students of the environmental concerns and issues and eventually encourage students' participation in environmental advocacies to protect and preserve our environment.

The mandate of the constitution to protect and preserve the environment anchored on the specific laws promulgated can be realized best if the cause of environmental problems be addressed on the micro level. One of the serious and prevalent environmental catastrophes is the mismanage on the dumping of garbage or trash that pollutes the land, water and atmosphere. The Municipality of Matnog in the Province of Sorsogon is not an exemption to this environmental problem. It was an eyesore to witness garbage scattered on the road brought about by massive flock of commuters who are waiting for their scheduled departure by ferry boats. In relation to this, improper waste disposal within the locality is rampant and the Local Government is oblivious in the importance of the implementation of the laws that intensify the need to maintain the balance of nature for its interminable existence.

Schools' garbage contributes to the volume of trash being disposed by the school personnel and students. From the observation of the researcher, solid waste management is one of the challenges of school administrators and educators that should be prioritized among the many school projects. This observation paves the way to the conduct this study for it is indeed vital to investigate how and why the problem exist so that effective and applicable solutions be proposed.

This study dealt on the assessment of the level of execution on SWM Act in the secondary schools in Matnog, Sorsogon. It targets to address the issue by proposing timely and feasible programs and intervention to ensure that said law will be implemented to the fullest. The researcher, as an environmental activist, is certainly firm in his decision to conduct this study because of its usefulness to the environment and its positive impact on the lives of the students, school personnel and community members in general.

Since school is a venue for students to practice SWM, the researcher opted to conduct this study to instill love for nature and life. The identification of the level of implementation of SWM in the public secondary schools in the Municipality of Matnog is an effective step to provide solutions based on the finding of the study. An intensified action plan which itemizes all the activities, strategies, key persons involved, source of fund and mode of verification is indeed necessary as tangible and suitable answer to the problem.

Research Questions

This study attempted to assess the level of implementation of solid waste management in the four public secondary schools in the Municipality of Matnog, Province of Sorsogon in the school-year 2021-2022. In addition, this study provided inputs for the development of an intensified solid waste management action plan. Specifically, it answered the questions stated below:

1. What is the level of implementation of solid waste management in the secondary schools in Matnog, Sorsogon as perceived by students, teachers and school administrators in terms of:
 - 1.1. waste minimization,
 - 1.2. waste segregation,
 - 1.3. waste storage and collection, and
 - 1.4. waste disposal?
2. Is there a significant difference between the perception of students and teachers, and between the teachers and schools'?

administrators in the implementation of solid waste management along with the identified variables?

3. What intensified action plan can be proposed based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive research design in which a questionnaire was used. Descriptive research establishes an association between variables where subjects of the study are usually measured once (Silvestre, 2020). Specifically, this study dealt with identifying the level of implementation of solid waste management in the public secondary schools in Matnog along waste minimization, segregation, storage and collection and disposal.

The respondents who were included in this study were the school administrators, faculty, and students of Matnog public secondary schools. To obtain information about the level of implementation of solid waste management, the respondents were asked to assess their understanding based on the self – assessment rating scale given to them. The level of implementation was measured based on the answered questionnaire.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the school administrators, high school teachers, and Grade 11 and 12 students of Matnog National High School, Tiong Hen So Memorial High School, Culasi National High School, and Sua National High School. These numbers reflected in Table 1 were normally distributed since they were taken from the total population through non – probability sampling technique.

Table 1 below showed the respondents of this study. It is visible that there were five (5) school administrators, twenty-eight (28) high school teachers, and one hundred eighty (180) grade 11 and grade 12 students. This sample size calculation was undertaken using the Slovin's formula.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent (%)</i>
School Administrator	5	2
High School Teachers	28	13
Grade 11 and 12 Students	180	85
Total	213	100

Instrument

The researcher adopted the questionnaire from the manual of the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR). This tool was utilized by the researcher since it is aligned to the assessment on the level of implementation of solid waste management in Matnog Public Secondary High Schools. This also underwent content validity by the adviser and those with background in waste management system. In addition, the congruency and appropriateness of its content to the problem of this study was validated and scrutinized by Dr. Salvador Gacis, Master-Teacher II of Matnog National High School.

The adopted questionnaire identified the respondents' perception on the level of implementation of solid waste management in terms of waste minimization, waste segregation, waste storage and collection, and waste disposal by checking the box 5 for very highly implemented, 4 for highly implemented, 3 for moderately implemented, 2 for slightly implemented, and 1 for not implemented. Each item was prepared in the simplest way to facilitate the understanding of every respondent.

To check the reliability of the instrument, a dry run was conducted on February 25, 2022, to ten (10) selected teachers and twenty (20) students of Matnog National High school who were randomly selected and were not identified as respondents of the study. The result yielded positive implication that the tool is accurate and plausible to be administered to the identified respondents of this study. However, slight revisions and improvement were made in accordance with the suggestions and recommendations given by the researcher's adviser and panel members. Soon after, the instrument was finalized and distributed to the target respondents.

Procedure

The administrators, teachers and students were the respondents of this study. Prior to data gathering, the researcher sought a letter of permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study and administer the questionnaires to the chosen respondents on January 24, 2022.

The reliability of the instrument was conducted on February 25, 2022 which resulted to positive implication that the instrument is accurate and plausible.

Next, the researcher presented the letter granting the authority to conduct the study to the principals of Matnog Secondary Schools. Then, the researcher personally distributed the questionnaires to the respondents. One week was given to the respondents to answer the questionnaire to give them ample time to answer the instrument. On April 14, 2022, the researcher retrieved all the questionnaires and started sorting out the data.

Since the researcher needed to assess the veracity of respondents' answers, he also conducted interview with some of these individuals. He met and talked with one school head, 1 head teacher, 5 classroom teachers and 10 students from April 25 to May 27, 2022. For almost a month, the researcher patiently appeared and communicated with the interviewees depending on the availability of the respondents.

Data Analysis

All the data that were collected served as the basis to verify the level of implementation of the Solid Waste Management in the Public Secondary Schools of Matnog, Sorsogon. After the collection of data, they were organized, tabulated, and analyzed. The following statistical treatments were used:

To interpret the result, a five-point Likert scale was used on the level of implementation of waste minimization, waste segregation, waste storage and collection and waste disposal in the four public secondary schools in the municipality of Matnog. Additionally, the weighted mean was used to determine the level of implementation of solid waste management along the four variables. To interpret the results, the following scale and interpretation was used:

Table 2. *Scale, Range, and Verbal Interpretation*

Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.20 – 5.00	Very Highly Implemented (VHI)
4	3.40 – 4.19	Highly Implemented (HI)
3	2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Implemented (MI)
2	1.80 – 2.59	Slightly Implemented (SI)
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Implemented (NI)

ANOVA. It is used to determine the significant differences among the perceptions of administrators, teachers and students on the level of implementation of solid waste management, ANOVA: Single Factor was utilized where the data analysis ToolPak in the excel was used.

Ethical Considerations

As part of ethical considerations in conducting this research, the researcher provided respondents the details of the study when they were asked for consent to partake in this research. In addition, to ensure confidentiality of the data gathered and to protect the respondent's identity, the researcher used pseudo names as reflected in the presentation and analysis of data. Moreover, respondents were not coerced specially during the interview process when they preferred not to elaborate some points. Also, the researcher valued and considered the convenience of the respondents specially in setting the time and place of the discussion process.

Results and Discussion

This section consists of the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered. The study made use of appropriate tables for clearer understanding of the results.

Level of Implementation of SWM in the public secondary schools in Matnog, Sorsogon by students, teachers, and school-administrators

This study also presents the following: (1) Level of Implementation of Solid Waste Management in the Public Secondary Schools in Matnog, Sorsogon as Perceived by Students, Teachers and School Administrators in Terms of Waste Minimization, Waste Segregation, Waste Storage and Collection, and Waste Disposal; (2) ANOVA Single Factor Results for Perception of Teachers and Students as well as Teachers and School Administrators on Solid Waste Management Implementation.

To provide sufficient and relevant data regarding the implementation of solid waste management, it is appropriate to identify the level of the respondents' awareness on the said program. This initiative would convince every individual, group, and entities to be involved in the successful operation of the program since those who will benefit of its positive result will be the community and the world at large.

The table 3 to 6 present the results of the perceptions of the groups of respondents on the level of implementation of Solid Waste Management.

Along Waste Minimization. Students, teachers, and school administrators comprise the entire population in school which could be of great help in minimizing waste inside the school premises. Collecting their point of view regarding the implementation of waste minimization in the school would provide ample information for concerned individuals to solve issues regarding SWM.

Table 3.1 presents the level of implementation of SWM along waste minimization as perceived by the three sets of respondents. The figures display that on the part of school administrators, two indicators are very highly implemented, namely food caterers should use reusable food containers and promote avoidance of single use disposable products and packaging materials. Furthermore, two of the indicators are highly implemented which range from 3.40-4.00. These indicators include use recyclables as seed beds in the nursery or gardens, encourage students to bring trash-free baon, school canteen shall use reusable food containers and avoid selling processed

food wrapped in non-recyclable packaging and use of refillable dispensers. Additionally, the table clearly exhibits that one indicator falls on moderately implemented, which has a weighted mean of 3.20. Finally, administrators got a mean average of 3.80 and is interpreted as highly implemented.

Meanwhile, the data above also present teachers' perception on the level of implementation on SWM along waste minimization. Five indicators are moderately implemented which range from 2.86 to 3.21. However, only one indicator is highly implemented with 3.50 WM and one indicator is slightly implemented. Lastly, this set of respondents got a mean average of 2.98 with a verbal interpretation of moderately implemented.

Table 3.1. *Level of Implementation of SWM Along Waste Minimization*

Waste Minimization	Respondents							
	Student		Teacher		Administrator			
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI		
1. Food caterers should use reusable food containers.	3.21	MI	3.50	HI	4.20	VHI		
2. Promote avoidance of single use disposable products and packaging materials.	2.74	MI	3.21	MI	4.20	VHI		
3. Use recyclables as seed beds in the nursery or garden.	2.51	SI	3.11	MI	4.00	HI		
4. Encourage student to bring trash-free 'baon'.	2.26	SI	3.11	MI	4.00	HI		
5. School canteen shall use reusable food containers and avoid selling processed food wrapped in non-recyclable packaging.	2.18	SI	2.68	MI	3.60	HI		
6. Use of refillable dispensers (food and water dispensers)	1.88	SI	2.86	MI	3.40	HI		
7. During events and meetings, consumables such as bottled water, coffee, sugar, and creamer in sachets should be avoided.	1.67	NI	2.36	SI	3.20	MI		
	Mean (Average)		2.35	SI	2.98	MI	3.80	HI

Legend: VI: Verbal Interpretation; 4.20 – 5.00, Very Highly Implemented (VHI); 3.40 – 4.19, Highly Implemented (HI); 2.60 – 3.39, Moderately Implemented (MI); 1.80 – 2.59, Slightly Implemented (SI); 1.00 – 1.79, Not Implemented (NI)

Additionally, it is noticeable that out of the seven indicators included, students' perception shows that food caterers should use reusable food containers ranked first with 3.21 weighted mean and with a description of moderately implemented. This is followed by promoting avoidance of single use disposable products and packaging materials with 2.74 weighted mean and is described as moderately implemented. In addition, using recyclables as seed beds in the nursery or garden got 2.51 WM, school canteen shall use reusable food containers and avoid selling processed food wrapped in non-recyclable packaging got 2.18 WM, and use of refillable dispensers got 1.88. Furthermore, only one indicator is considered not implemented with 1.67 WM. To conclude, students got a mean average of 2.35 and interpreted as slightly implemented.

It can be deduced from the table that school administrators have high regard to waste minimization as it is implemented in the secondary schools in Matnog, Sorsogon. It can be concluded that school administrators are confident to admit that minimizing the use of non-biodegradable is given emphasis in the school they are assigned to. This could be manifested on the different programs they initiated such as students bring their own glasses instead of using plastic containers and utensils. This is visibly seen in school canteen, student lounge and waiting shed and area.

Delving deeper on the result of this study, the researcher further claims that the support extended by the school administrators on the implementation of SWM is anchored on DepEd Order No. 5 s. 2014. This order reiterates that every school needs to practice waste management philosophies, such as minimization, segregation, reduction, recycling, re-use and composting to instill environmental awareness among students. In line with this, school administrators' resourcefulness paves way for inculcating the values of love for mother nature and humanity among 21st century learners.

Remarkably, the given result is associated with the study conducted by Kamaruddin, Siti & Omar, Dasimah. (2011) that administrators are more enthusiastic about school communities participating in recycling programs as compared to recycling activities run by other volunteers in the community. Administrators perceive that recycling effort should be the responsibility of each individual but the lack of commitment from the public in general to participate, misuse of recycling infrastructure, financial constraints and the absence of proper guidelines hamper many programs sustainability. Generally, their main concern is to ensure waste is collected and the works monitored while communities should champion these activities with minimal interventions from the authority.

In addition, the figures above reveal that teachers show positive reaction on the idea that waste minimization is being addressed in the different secondary schools in Matnog, Sorsogon. This is evident in the first indicator which gained a higher weighted mean and as classified as highly implemented. This result could be due to teachers' awareness on the need to fully implement SWM in school campus to educate learners on its importance, thereby influencing the latter to practice waste minimization even at homes. Moreover, this good result proves that it is possible to intensify waste minimization in the school level, since teachers see the need to implement the program in various day to day encounters such as during teachers and students' activities and meetings.

During conversation with a science teacher, he pointed out that: Waste minimization is indeed necessary to avoid piling out of garbage. In this manner, we are also saving mother nature from her destruction. We, teachers, are powerful catalyst of change in this aspect. Simple yet effective approach could be done and one of these is waste minimization. Start with ourselves and next, let us influence our

students to reduce the use of plastics and other non-recyclable materials so we could also help in maintaining balance in the ecosystem. (Sir Drei)

The result presented conforms with the study conducted by Baysen and Baysen (2020). Findings reveal that there is a variation in awareness among the teachers regarding waste and WM, including conceptions, misconceptions, and the relations among them. The teachers' level of awareness is captured in three categories: low awareness, awareness, and high awareness. Waste awareness includes the waste definition and waste examples, while awareness of WM includes the WM definition, WM importance, WM methods, and WM responsibility.

Furthermore, it can be deduced that the level of students' perception regarding waste minimization in school is average. This means that the waste minimization in the secondary schools in the municipality of Matnog is not fully prioritized by the school administrators. The use of plastic containers, disposable products, non-recyclable packaging and sachets was not controlled and so trashes, and garbage continued to pile up. In this scenario, students can even attest that these phenomena really happened in the school premise. As a matter of fact, Abner, a senior high school student of Matnog National High School, mentioned that "it was easy for us to buy coffee in the canteen because of the styro cups instead of the real cups which needed to be washed after using".

Accordingly, Helmer (2020) emphasized that although a report by Clean Water Action found that manufacturing conventional polystyrene products used less energy and water than paper or cornstarch alternatives, the single-use plastic is ubiquitous in landfills where it takes thousands of years to decompose, contaminates soil and water and pose hazards to wildlife. Coffee and other hot liquids can cause styrene to leach from cups; the chemical has been linked to a host of health problems from impaired concentration and nervous system effects to cancer.

Table 3.2. ANOVA: Single Factor results of students, teacher, and school administrators on Waste Minimization

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Fcomputed</i>	<i>Fcritical</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Student	2.350				
Teacher	2.976	25.39	3.682	Reject the H0	Significant
Administrator	3.800				

Table 3.2 showed F-test results of students, teachers, and school administrators on waste minimization. Specifically, the mean of the students is 2.350, faculty is 2.976, and administrator is 3.800. In addition, the computed F value is 25.39 and the critical F value is 3.682. Furthermore, since the computed F value is greater than the critical F value then, the decision is to reject the null hypothesis which means that there is a significant difference between the students, teacher, and administrators in terms of waste minimization.

The data revealed that the three sets of respondents have substantially different answers from one another. Among them, administrators believe that waste minimization is really practiced in the school and interpreted as highly implemented. However, teachers' responses are interpreted as moderately implemented while students fall under slightly implemented. These significant differences are clear manifestations that the implementation of waste minimization in school set-up is not successful since majority of the respondents are students, who believed that this aspect of SWM is not given much emphasis.

This result is backed up by the utterances of a senior high school student stating that: I don't think waste minimization is really practiced in our school since styro cups, and plastics are frequently used in the canteen. Whenever you buy coffee, styro cups will be used and foods such as kakanin were wrapped in plastic cellophane. Also, when you buy breakfast, the crew will always use styropor to avoid washing of dishes instead just disposed them in trash bin. I and my classmates experienced this and it's a common scenario in our school. (John Paul)

In connection with this outcome, students' responses call for immediate and effective resolution on the realization of the SWM' goals. Although, it is evident that administrators have positive views on waste minimization being implemented in the school, the data undeniably warrant that heads of school should be vigilant and serious in the call for minimizing the use of non-biodegradable products in the school campus.

This scenario is in consonance with the findings of Smyth, Fredeen, and Booth (2010) in their study on reducing solid waste in higher education. This study determined that during the 2007–2008 academic year the Prince George campus produced between 1.2 and 2.2 metric tons of waste per week, of which more than 70% could have been diverted through waste reduction, recycling and composting activities. Paper and paper products, disposable drink containers and compostable organic material represented three of the most significant material types for targeted waste reduction and recycling efforts.

Interestingly, Business Waste (2024) emphasized that schools have a role to reduce and recycle waste and at the same time educate learners to be eco-conscious citizens who understand their function to protect mother nature. Truly, an effective implementation of SWM plan in school would ensure achievement of goals and objectives thereby creating safe and secure environment both for teachers, personnel and students.

Along Waste Segregation. Waste segregation is one of the waste management principles that plays a n important role in the success of the program. This includes sorting out of waste into different items which may start in the school or household, collected by means of

collection schemes and separated in material recovery facilities. In addition to this, correct final disposal of waste means achievement on the part of all the concerned individuals from one department to another.

Table 4.1 shows the data on the level of implementation of SWM along waste segregation as perceived by the school administrators, faculty members and students. As perceived by the school administrators, data reveals that properly labeled garbage receptacles gained a perfect WM of 5.00 and classified as very highly implemented. This is followed by students and school personnel are practicing segregation with 4.80 WM and categorized as very highly implemented.

Two more indicators are considered highly implemented, ranging from 3.80 – 4.00, namely established a MRF to reduce waste generated from various sources and students and school personnel are practicing segregation. Last of all is conducted trainings and information campaign on comprehensive SWM with 3.20 WM and is classified as moderately implemented. To sum up, administrators got a mean average of 4.16 and is interpreted as highly implemented.

Table 4.1. *Level of Implementation of SMW Along Waste Segregation*

Waste Segregation	Respondents							
	Student		Teacher		Administrator			
	WM	I	WM	I	WM	I		
1. Properly labeled garbage receptacles.	3.90	HI	4.04	HI	5.00	VHI		
2. Students and school personnel are practicing segregation.	3.64	HI	3.96	HI	4.80	VHI		
3. Available garbage receptacles for biodegradable, nonbiodegradable and recyclable on strategic areas in the school	3.51	HI	3.21	MI	4.00	HI		
4. Established a Material Recovery Facility to reduce waste generated from various sources.	2.81	MI	2.14	SI	3.80	HI		
5. Conducted trainings and information campaign on comprehensive solid waste management.	1.92	SI	2.07	SI	3.20	MI		
	Mean (Average)		3.16	MI	3.08	MI	4.16	HI

Legend: VI: Verbal Interpretation; 4.20 – 5.00, Very Highly Implemented (VHI); 3.40 – 4.19, Highly Implemented (HI); 2.60 – 3.39, Moderately Implemented (MI); 1.80 – 2.59, Slightly Implemented (SI); 1.00 – 1.79, Not Implemented (NI)

Furthermore, the afore mentioned table also portrays teachers' perception on the level of SWM implementation along waste segregation in the different secondary schools in the municipality of Matnog in Sorsogon province. The figures show that out of five indicators two are highly implemented that range from 3.96 - 4.04, namely. These indicators are properly labeled garbage receptacles and students and school personnel are practicing segregation. In addition, only one is

moderately implemented specifically available garbage receptacles for biodegradable, nonbiodegradable and recyclable on strategic areas in school with 3.21 WM. Furthermore, two indicators are slightly implemented specifically, conduct of training and information campaign, and establish a material a MRF to reduce waste that range from 2.07 – 2.14. In closing, teachers' perception on the level of implementation of SWM along waste segregation got 3.08 mean average and interpreted as moderately implemented.

Likewise, it is very evident that on the part of students, out of the seven indicators, 3 are highly implemented with WM ranging from 3.51- 3.90. These indicators are properly labeled garbage receptacles, students and school personnel are practicing segregation and available garbage receptacles for biodegradable, nonbiodegradable and recyclable on strategic areas in the school. Along with this, one indicator is moderately implemented with 2.81 WM which is established a material recovery facility to reduce waste generated from various sources. Lastly, only one indicator got slightly implemented description with 1.92 WM and this is conducted training and information campaign on comprehensive SWM. Summing up this result, students got a mean average of 3.16 and is interpreted as moderately implemented.

It can be deduced from the table that school administrators are certain that waste segregation is really implemented in school. This is evident on the result wherein almost all the indicators received high weighted mean. The reason for this may be linked to the idea that SWM specifically waste segregation is given attention by school heads. This is also evident and given emphasis on the different programs by the Department of Education such as Brigada Eskwela wherein waste segregation is one of the components being evaluated. In addition, this aspect is also indicated and practiced in the several programs in the Division of Sorsogon such as Ligtas-Gayon program for the SY 2022-2023.

During focus group discussion, one of the school heads admitted that: As school heads, it is our prime duty to implement and spearhead programs downloaded by the Department of Education. One of these programs include the implementation of SWM particularly on waste segregation. In this phase, we encouraged teachers to apply waste segregation from the classroom up to MRF. In this manner, students are trained to segregate their waste on trash bins which are labelled as biodegradable, nonbiodegradable and recyclable. This has been done for years and students are accustomed to it. (Ms. Maria)

The scenario presented is in consonance with the study conducted by Punongbayan et al. (2014). In their study, findings reveal that Waste Management practices of Lyceum of the Philippines University Batangas are effective in terms of collection, disposable, recovery, and processing as perceived by the respondents. The heads of the departments, as the respondents, moderately agreed that there are problems occurring in the waste management practices of LPU-B, specifically that disposal area of waste materials is not

strategically located. Moreover, though there are means of recovering and reusing such waste but there were not strictly implemented. There are significant relationships in the waste management practices of LPU-B in terms of collection, disposal and recovery and processing.

Interestingly, the result points toward the idea that teachers have variations on their feedback regarding the level of implementation of waste segregation in school. This is acceptable and tolerable since these teacher-samples came from the four different secondary schools and each school has modified means of waste segregation. Moreover, this variation could be due to dissimilarity of the prioritized programs in the schools which means some schools might have fully implemented SWM, and others were not. However, it is incontestable to conclude that teachers' response on waste segregation is good and that intensifying its implementation is possible.

This scenario is evident in the utterance of one of the teachers in Matnog National High School proclaiming that "it sometimes saddens me that sometimes waste segregation is not fully given emphasis by some teachers and students, and that their implementation is not consistent, they will just cooperate if someone will advise them to do so" (Mr. Jose).

Remarkably, the situation presented above is in line with the proposition of Earth Reminder (2022) emphasizing that environmental education is now a pillar of the primary education system. Given the current state of nature, environmental education takes a more critical role. School children need to understand the importance of nature, its resources and its plant and animal life. Teachers in this regard play a significant role. They are the ones who could shape the minds of young ones from early days to be responsible towards nature. They must assume the responsibility of instilling the values and ethics needed to protect the environment.

In addition, looking intently at the data presented, it is visible that students' level of perception along waste segregation is high and stable. This result manifests that indicators for this WM principle are evident in the school. For instance, labeled garbage receptacles and material recovery facility are found in the school and common sights among the students. Students' honest evaluation in this part is an outcome of their involvement in the campus where SWM, specifically waste segregation as being practiced consistently and religiously.

A senior high school student, when asked during an interview, truthfully answered that: In our school and even in our classroom, we have trash bins with labels. such biodegradable, non-biodegradable, and recyclable. Our teachers always remind us to segregate our trash and we should be accountable of our actions that could affect mother nature. That's why, every time we have plastics or paper with us, we see to it that we put them in the right bin. (Maria Ana)

This statement only proves that students have positive feedback regarding the implementation of SWM explicitly waste segregation. They have inculcated the value of respecting mother earth since the school trained them to be environment warriors.

The above results are in consonance with the study of Molina and Catan (2021) on Solid Waste Management Awareness and Practices. Result shows that senior high school students have enough knowledge in terms on definition of solid waste, effect of improper solid waste disposal, solid waste prohibited activities, school initiatives towards solid waste, importance of solid waste management and students' responsibilities. The result also shows that students have good solid waste management practices in terms on segregation, reduction, reuse, recycle and disposal.

Table 4.2. ANOVA: Single Factor results of students, teacher, and school administrators on Waste Segregation

Respondents	Mean	F _{computed}	F _{critical}	Decision	Interpretation
Student	3.156				
Teacher	3.084	2.332	4.257	Do not reject the H ₀	Not Significant
Administrator	4.160				

The table above illustrates the results of students, teacher, and school administrators on waste segregation. The mean for students is 3.156, for teacher is 3.084 and administrator is 4.160. The computed F value is 2.332 while the critical F is 4.257. It is said that when the computed F value is less than the critical F value the decision is do not reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, it is not significant or there is no significant difference between the students, teacher, and administrators on waste segregation.

The data further pointed out that in terms of waste segregation, the three sets of respondents have a common understanding on the implementation of this SWM aspect in the school set up. Additionally, it can be concluded that waste segregation is visible and functional in the secondary schools of Matnog II district. This also intensifies SWM scheme as efficacious and outstanding since all individuals in school partake in the realization of this SWM goal.

This outcome was manifested in the statement of one of the faculty members asserting that "it is good that in every classroom there are trash bins for the various types of waste, so students are aware of their responsibility to segregate bio and non-biodegradable materials."

In connection to the above discussion, the study of Molina & Catan (2021) revealed that students have adequate knowledge in terms of the definition and importance of SWM, ill-effect of inappropriate solid waste disposal, solid waste prohibited activities, school activities and programs towards SWM and students' responsibilities. Nevertheless, the study of Ifegbesan (2008) can be linked with the data presented in the sense that findings of his study proved that secondary school students from the sampled zones were aware of

waste problems on their school compounds but possessed poor waste management practices. Significant relationships were observed between students’ sex, age and class and their level of awareness, knowledge and practices of waste management.

Along Waste Storage and Collection. The roles played by all the stakeholders in solid waste management are indeed vital to ensure its effectiveness. There is a great possibility that if all the people involved, religiously work on their part, this endeavor will bring good results to the school in terms of properly storing and collecting garbage and waste materials that pose dangers to the surroundings.

Table 5.1, presents the administrators, faculty, and students’ perception on the level of implementation of SWM along waste storage and collection. It reflects that for school administrators, out of the seven indicators included, three are very highly implemented and the other four indicators are highly implemented. Alongside with this, two indicators gained a perfect WM, namely garbage receptacles are placed in strategic areas of the school and the school designates or assigns an area as Material Recovery Facility (MRF) that will serve as storage areas. Finally, a mean average of 4.14 was recorded and interpreted as highly implemented.

The figures point to the realization that school administrators are undisputable that waste storage and collection is prioritized and given emphasis in the secondary schools in the municipality of Matnog. Additionally, the data reveals that among all the SMW principles, waste storage and collection gained the highest attention and assurance among school administrators. This result could be attributed to the serious implementation of SMW in the school level and the participation of the school administrators in the program.

Table 5.1. Level of Implementation of SWM Along Waste Storage and Collection

Waste Storage and Collection	Respondents					
	Student		Teacher		Administrator	
	WM	I	WM	I	WM	I
1. Garbage receptacles are placed in strategic areas of the school.	3.66	HI	3.75	HI	5.00	VHI
2. The school designates or assigns an area as Material Recovery Facility (MRF) that will serve as storage areas.	3.52	HI	3.61	HI	5.00	VHI
3. Garbage collections are done on a regular basis by the municipal garbage collectors.	3.52	HI	3.61	HI	4.80	VHI
4. Generated wastes are placed along the collection route of the garbage collection vehicle.	2.88	MI	2.39	SI	3.60	HI
5. Generated wastes shall be brought and stored by the teachers and class advisers inside the garbage receptacles provided for.	2.83	MI	2.36	SI	3.60	HI
6. All students and personnel are enjoined to place all garbage inside the garbage receptacles provided for by the school.	2.81	MI	2.07	SI	3.60	HI
7. Appointed a school representative to become a regular member of Solid Waste Management Committee of its host barangay as mandated in RA 9003.	2.17	SI	1.86	SI	3.40	HI
Mean (Average)	3.06	MI	2.81	MI	4.14	HI

Legend: VI: Verbal Interpretation; 4.20 – 5.00, Very Highly Implemented (VHI); 3.40 – 4.19, Highly Implemented (HI); 2.60 – 3.39, Moderately Implemented (MI); 1.80 – 2.59, Slightly Implemented (SI); 1.00 – 1.79, Not Implemented (NI)

Interestingly, it is good to note that school administrators have fully accepted the responsibility of implementing SWM in the school level. In this manner, it is of great help to successfully implement the program in a wider scope since it has already been established in a specific department or location. As a result, this will pave the way for a better understanding and linkage between the school and the community in relation to solid waste storage and collection.

This outcome has been strengthened by the utterance of one of the school administrators affirming that: SWM should be implemented in the school so that learners will develop their respect and love for Mother Earth. If learners were trained to follow the various principles, then they could influence their family and all their peers to do the same. Along waste storage and disposal, connection between the school and the community should be reinforced with action and consistency, so that sustainability and other consequence will be achieved. (Ms. Minchin)

Accordingly, this result was supported by the New Zealand Ministry of Education (2024) pointing out that separating, reducing, reusing, recycling, and composting are good options for managing school waste. School authorities need to find ways to get rid of school waste with the least negative effects on the environment. separate organic waste like food scraps, plants, paper, and lawn clippings from other rubbish. The use of organic waste for composting and teaching students about how it works are necessary.

Meanwhile, the given records also display the level of implementation of SWM along waste storage and collection as perceived by the teachers. It can easily be seen that out of seven indicators, the first three gained WM ranging from 3.61-3.75 and are classified as highly implemented. In addition, the remaining four indicators are interpreted as slightly implemented with WM ranging from 1.86 to 2.39. To conclude, teachers’ perception was computed with 2.81 mean average and interpreted as moderately implemented.

Accordingly, the data implied that teachers have high and positive feedback regarding the waste storage and collection in the different secondary schools in the municipality of Matnog. This principle of SWM is given stress and importance in every school that is why teachers are indeed sure of its implementation in the school level. Waste storage and collection has been widely practiced and its prominence is experienced by internal stakeholders. In the same manner, this is supported by the indicator which got the highest WM which is, all students and personnel are enjoined to place all garbage inside the garbage receptacles provided by the school. This

outcome is reasonable and acceptable for it projects teachers' involvement in this eco-friendly activity.

However, it is a wake-up call for SWM team of every school to further intensify its sanction to allow any of them to become a regular member of the barangay SMW Committee. This measure is imperative to have linkage between the school and the community for an enhanced SWM implementation. As a matter of fact, this indicator should be addressed properly as evident in the result presented.

In line with the abovementioned upshot, Maam Wency, a junior high school teacher mentioned that "for the successful implementation of SWM, linkage between the school and community should be given attention for smooth transaction especially on the waste collection, since the community has serious role to play in the process".

In essence, the study of Galarpe & Heyasa (2017) conforms with the results of this paper. Survey showed positive level of awareness, attitude, and practices of teachers towards SWM. Practices however were selectively better in some schools through establishing recycling and composting options. Generally, the absence of a recommended material recovery facility (MRF) was common. Present findings served as basis to review existing policy framework in DepEd and the local government units (LGUs) to support SWM in educational sectors.

In essence, the result clearly shows that along waste storage and collection, students' topmost indicator is garbage receptacles are place in strategic areas of the school with 3.66 WM and classified as highly implemented. This is followed by the school designates or assigns area for MRF with 3.52 WM and is categorized as highly implemented. Alongside with this is that garbage collections are done on a regular basis by the municipal garbage collectors which earned a WM of 3.52 and is considered as highly implemented. On the contrary, the indicator that gained the lowest WM of 2.17 and is categorized as slightly implemented is appoint a school representative to become a regular member of SWM Committee of its host barangay. Ultimately, the figures present that students got a mean average of 3.06 and is interpreted as moderately implemented.

It can be gleaned from the table that students have above average perception on the waste storage and collection in the identified secondary schools. This further implies that students were aware that municipal garbage collectors were seen in the school, barangays, and main streets who collect and deliver garbage to the dump sites. This scenario has been a usual view for learners and has become part of their normal community encounters. Remarkably, this scenario only attests that waste storage and collection in the secondary schools in the municipality of Matnog are implemented and visible.

The result presented can be associated to the response given by one of the officers of the School Government Council when asked during an informal talk.

In our school, the utility personnel collect all the garbage in each classroom and store them in the MRF, then garbage collector or dump truck from the municipality collects the stored waste/trash. They do this regularly and I witness this myself. (Arthur)

Interestingly, this set up is supported by the study of Catan & Molina stating that students are knowledgeable in the definition of SWM, importance of SWM, effect of improper solid waste disposal, solid waste prohibited activities, school initiatives towards solid waste, and students' responsibilities. Nevertheless, when it comes to the different laws relevant to SWM, unfortunately, students have low knowledge. Moreover, television or radio, parents, and social media are the sources of these awareness. The findings also suggest that students have good solid waste management practices in terms on segregation, reduction, reuse, recycle and disposal.

Table 5.2. ANOVA: Single Factor results of students, faculty, and school administrators on Waste Storage & Collection

Respondents	Mean	F _{computed}	F _{critical}	Decision	Interpretation
Student	3.056				
Teacher	2.807	6.701	3.682	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Administrator	4.143				

It can be seen from this table the results of students, teacher, and school administrators' perceptions on waste storage and collection. The mean of student is 3.056, faculty is 2.807, and administrator is 4.143. The computed F value is 6.701 while critical F value is 3.682. The decision is to reject the null hypothesis since the computed F value is greater than the critical F value. In this case, the result is significant or there is a significant difference between students, teacher, and administrators in terms of waste storage and collection.

Looking closely at the result, it can be inferred that the three sets of respondents have different assessments on the implementation of waste storage and collection in the secondary schools in Matnog II district. These variations could be credited to some factors such as respondents' level of awareness and involvement on this SWM aspect. Debrah, Vidal and Dinis (2020) conducted research targeting identification and analysis of students SWM knowledge, awareness, attitudes, and practice from 2010 to 2019 in identified developing countries. The outcome of the study proposes that high school and college students have positive environmental attitudes, and high awareness of environmental problems but a need for teachers to guide students on SWM practice is indeed crucial.

Based on the data presented, it is perceptible that administrators have the highest regard on the implementation of waste storage and collection in the school setting. This result is possible because they are very much aware of all the programs being implemented and one of these is the SWM. Since, school heads have control on the operation, they know exactly the details of this activity and they

thought that the program runs smoothly in the field. On the contrary, if other internal stakeholders are not participative in the operation; therefore, the implementation of waste storage and collection will not be materialized.

Accordingly, the lower perception of students and teachers on the implementation of waste storage and collection could be acceptable since they are not directly involved in these activities. The common scenario in the school is that waste storage is the responsibility of janitors and other school aides while waste collection is usually assigned to municipal garbage collectors. With this set up, only these persons involved and mentioned are well-informed in the operation.

Essentially, the thought presented above is in accordance with the idea of Waste Cost Solutions (2022) emphasizing that one of the main reasons why waste management is a problem at school is that there is often a lack of education on how to properly handle it. Without proper instruction, students are more likely to throw away recyclable items or use too much paper or plastic during lunchtime or other activities. Furthermore, teachers may not be aware of the importance of reducing their own classroom waste or the potential benefits of recycling. Without proper education, wasteful habits become ingrained in both students and staff members alike.

In the same manner, the non-involvement of students and teachers in waste storage and collection hinders them to fully understand the essentials of SWM.

Along Waste Disposal. One of the goals of SWM is to properly dispose waste and manage garbage to avoid catastrophic results for the world in the near future. Moreover, it also aims to take steps towards sustainability from human health to biodiversity conservation. In this regard, the school is a compelling venue for the implementation of this program with the support of its internal and external stakeholders.

Table 6.1 presents the level of implementation of SWM along waste disposal as perceived by the three sets of respondents. For school administrators, the figures clearly specify that the first indicator gained a very high implementation with a WM of 4.80. This indicator is hazardous wastes are disposed in accordance with the law and open burning of mixed SW is prohibited. This is followed by three indicators and are classified as highly implemented, which range from 3.40 to 3.60. In addition, the last two indicators are interpreted as moderately implemented with a WM of 3.20.

Table 6.1. *Level of Implementation of SWM Along Waste Disposal*

Waste Disposal	Respondents					
	Student		Teacher		Administrator	
	WM	I	WM	I	WM	I
1. Hazardous wastes are disposed in accordance with the laws, rules, regulations and guidelines of the concerned national agencies (EMB-DENR, DOH, PNRI).	3.43	HI	3.89	HI	4.80	VHI
2. Enforce prohibition of littering and burning of wastes	3.36	MI	3.11	MI	3.60	HI
3. Collection of solid waste is done in a manner that prevents the damage to the container and scattering of solid waste within the vicinity.	2.24	SI	2.64	MI	3.40	HI
4. Open burning of mixed solid wastes is prohibited.	2.20	SI	2.29	SI	3.40	HI
5. Establish aerobic or anerobic system for processing biodegradable wastes.	2.16	SI	2.21	SI	3.20	MI
6. Personnel directly handling the solid wastes are equipped with personal protective equipment/devices	2.01	SI	2.21	SI	3.20	MI
Mean (Average)	2.57	SI	2.73	MI	3.60	HI

Legend: VI: Verbal Interpretation; 4.20 – 5.00, Very Highly Implemented (VHI); 3.40 – 4.19, Highly Implemented (HI); 2.60 – 3.39, Moderately Implemented (MI); 1.80 – 2.59, Slightly Implemented (SI); 1.00 – 1.79, Not Implemented (NI)

The data implies that school administrators' perception regarding waste disposal is average. The four indicators which excel and categorized as moderately implemented summarize the main implication of the result. This phenomenon was established since school administrators have appointed key persons on the implementation of SWM particularly on the waste disposal. In this manner, school heads entrust the responsibility to these individuals to lead and take part in the various activities such as disposing the garbage. These key persons know better the details of the conduct of SWM than the school administrators. Finally, administrators earned 3.60 mean average and is interpreted as highly implemented.

In essence, a school administrator bravely admits that: For the program to work successfully, I assigned someone to look after the disposal of waste properly. This person oversees the place, time, and manner of disposal. He is also tasked to link with the municipal SWM for the transport of non-biodegradable wastes from school to the dump sites. In this way, the program will run smoothly and efficiently. (Sir Dante)

To support this claim, Panay News (2018) emphasized that school principals, the faculty, non-academic personnel, students, and parents should work together to cut the volume and toxicity of discards in schools. The principals can surely tap student governments, faculty clubs and the Parent-Teacher Associations. To further strengthen its implementation, the Department Order (D.O.) 5, Series of 2014, issued by the Department of Education provides for the "Implementing Guidelines on the Integration of Gulayan sa Paaralan, Solid Waste Management and Tree Planting Under the National Greening Program."

The table above also shows teachers' perception on the level of implementation of SWM along waste disposal. It can be noted that the

first indicator got 3.89 WM and interpreted as highly implemented. Furthermore, the second and third indicators are interpreted as moderately implemented with WM ranging from 2.64 to 3.11. On the contrary, the fourth to sixth indicators are slightly implemented with WM ranging from 2.21 to 2.29. Finally, 2.73 average mean was recorded for this set of respondents and is interpreted as moderately implemented.

The data suggest that teachers have a not so high awareness on the waste disposal activity in the secondary schools in the municipality of Matnog. This conclusion is due to the fact that teachers are more focused on orienting students and disseminating input about waste segregation and waste disposal is not always practiced because there are personnel who are assigned to do the latter. This scenario is practical and acceptable because usually the utility and other personnel assigned to SWM administered the waste disposal.

This observation was given emphasis in the study of Mihai, Banica, & Grozavu (2019) regarding open burning. Although the set-up maybe different, however, it is good to note that school and community are both aware of the danger of open burning. As a matter of fact, waste constitutes an additional pollution source for NO₂, SO₂, CO or greenhouse gases (CO₂, CH₄). The improvement of collection efficiency across the most populated communes is imperative to reduce the negative impact of backyard burning practices across the county in the short term supported by the better implementation of waste collection schemes through the new regional integrated waste management system. There is a serious knowledge gap concerning air pollution sources in rural areas of Romania, where backyard burning could play a key role due to the poor waste management infrastructure.

Meanwhile, the figures above also show the perception of the students on the level of implementation of SWM along waste disposal. It is perceptible that the first indicator got a WM of 3.43 and is interpreted as highly implemented. This is followed by enforce prohibition of littering and burning of waste with a WM of 3.36 and interpreted as moderately implemented. However, the data also speak that four out of six indicators fall on slightly implemented with a WM ranging from 2.01 - 2.24. In conclusion, students' perception got a mean average of 2.57 and is interpreted as slightly implemented.

It can be deduced from the statistics presented that students are not so much aware of how waste is disposed in and from the school up to the dump sites. This outcome is a manifestation that students are more focused on waste segregation than the latter. This phenomenon is acceptable since learners are tasked and guided mostly on segregating waste than disposing them. Nevertheless, it should be given emphasis that learners should also know and be involved on how waste is disposed properly.

Remarkably, the four indicators classified as slightly implemented signify that students lack information and technical terms used in SWM were unknown words to them. For instance, these words were open burning, aerobic and anaerobic system, and personal protective device. In this case, orientation of students should be conducted in order to acquaint them of these terms and master how waste disposal is implemented in the school up to the municipality level.

Waste disposal as discussed by Flash Education (2020) allows students to partake and play a very important and significant role in waste management. It includes utilizing their belongings like paper, pencils, and pens to the maximum and produce less amounts of wastes. Also, students can keep their classrooms and houses clean by not littering things here and there, dispose wastes generated in school or house and reuse certain wastes to make productive items like empty cans can be used as pen stands.

Table 6.2. ANOVA: Single Factor Results of Students, Teacher, and School Administrators on Waste Disposal

Respondents	Mean	F _{computed}	F _{critical}	Decision	Interpretation
Student	2.567				
Teacher	2.725	8.869	3.885	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Administrator	3.600				

Table 6.2 shows the results of students, teacher, and school administrators on waste disposal. The mean of student is 2.567 while the teacher is 2.725 and the administrator is 3.600. The computed F value is 8.869 and the critical F value is 3.885. The decision for this case is to reject the null hypothesis since the computed F value is greater than the critical F value which means significant.

Therefore, there is no significant difference between students, teachers, and school administrators on waste disposal.

The figures above disclose the perception of the three sets of respondents on the implementation of SWM along waste disposal in the secondary schools in Matnog II district. It is noticeable that respondents have uniform assessments on how waste are disposed in the school level. Thus, it can be concluded that waste disposal is highly and successfully implemented in secondary schools.

This positive result can be credited to the respondents' awareness on the school actions and activities related to waste disposal. The constant reminder and follow up of school administrators on the regular and consistent disposition of garbage by assigned entities are success indicators that are directly observed by internal stakeholders. To support this statement, ETM recycling (2020) pointed out that effective waste management comes in many forms according to the scale or scenario of waste creation for instance, effective waste disposal can be as minimal as individuals putting waste in a bin and not littering.

In connection to the above-mentioned result, this present study concludes that waste disposal although may be considered a complex process could be accomplished in the school setting if every individual and entity partake and involve in the implementation of SWM.

Considering the importance of SWM, Castillo (2023) stated that one of the most effective ways to preserve the environment is through proper waste management. Efficient waste management programs can influence positive changes in the environment and contribute to ecological sustainability toward a better future for our children and our planet.

Significant Differences on the perception of students, teachers, and school administrators on Solid Waste Management Implementation using ANOVA

The implication of SWM in maintaining and restoring the ecological balance has been widely accepted by different groups, movements, and societies. Its positive impact comes from a series of simple yet efficient steps to be done consistently and thoroughly by concerned individuals, wherein bluntly speaking, everyone is involved. These phases, prevention, reuse, recycle, recovery and disposal, lead to a safe and better place to live in and abundant resources for man's consumption.

Table 7 displays the results on the perception of administrators, teachers, and students on the implementation of SMW using ANOVA Single Factor. It can clearly be seen that three sets of respondents have same counts of twenty-five (25), however the sum of square varies such as that school administrators got 98, teachers with 72.25, and students with 69.02. Meanwhile, school administrators have a variance of 0.403333333, teacher with 0.464091667 and students with 0.450391.

Table 7. ANOVA: Single Factor Results for Perception of Students, Teachers, and Administrators on Solid Waste Management Implementation

Respondents	Mean	F _{computed}	F _{critical}	Decision	Interpretation
Student	2.782				
Teacher	2.898	22.967	3.124	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Administrator	3.926				

In essence, the ANOVA table shows that the sums of squares for between group is 20.17781067, with the degrees of freedom of 2 and with a mean square of 10.088905. Meanwhile, within groups have 31.627584 sums of squares, 72 for degrees of freedom and 0.439272 for mean square. However, it is noted that between groups has a computed F value of 22.976331 and that is greater than critical F value of 3.123907449. In this case, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Additionally, to further discover which among the three groups; school administrators versus teachers, school administrators versus students and teachers versus students, have significant difference, post-HOC test (Bonferroni) was applied. Based on the table, it is understandable that school administrators versus teachers and administrators versus students have significant difference on their perception on the level of SWM implementation in the municipality of Matnog, second district. This further means that rejecting the hypothesis is a must. Nevertheless, teachers versus students have no significant difference and therefore, the null hypothesis is not rejected.

In line with the last table, the mean of student is 2.782 while the teacher is 2.898 and the administrator is 3.926. The computed F value is 22.967 and the critical F value is 3.124. The decision for this case is to reject the null hypothesis since the computed F value is greater than the critical F value which means significant. Therefore, there is no significant difference between students, teachers, and school administrators on their perception about the implementation of SWM in the secondary schools in Matnog II district.

Accordingly, the statistics above support the claim that the three sets of respondents have common perception in the implementation of SWM in the school setting. This is acceptable because they are the active participants in the completion of programs and activities related to SWM. In this manner, these individuals were also the contributing and controlling factors in waste production, segregation, collection, and disposal. Thus, there is indeed composite perception and feedback from all the sets of respondents.

However, it is irrefutable that school administrators have the highest weighted mean when it comes to assessing the implementation of SWM in the school. This result is realistic because school heads are usually the initiators on the implementation of programs and activities therefore, they expect positive result from other internal stakeholders. With this setup, school administrators are optimistic that SWM operates smoothly in the campus and given priority by concerned individuals.

Delving deeper into the result, Ruiz, Sagara, Tumalak, and Discipulo's (2021) study discovered the level of awareness and practices of the respondents on SWM. Based on the result, findings reveal that the awareness and practices towards SWM as perceived by the students, teachers, and administrators have significantly not differed. Teachers and School Administrators had no significant differences, and only the students had a difference in their SWM practices. Accordingly, the study found out that both academics, instructors, and administrators have lack of understanding about SWM. In essence, the researchers highly suggest that all the respondents should undergo seminar that focuses on SWM policies, discipline, proper disposal, and segregation of waste. This result does not support the data found in this present study, wherein school administrators and teachers have significant difference in SWM implementation.

Remarkably, Diola (2021) studied the perception of school administrators in terms of amount of waste generated; reduction of solid waste generation; solid waste management practices and experiences. It was found out that school administrators are aware of the amount of solid waste generated, the principals wish to comply with the existing laws and policies, waste reduction is being taught but not observed, there is a segregation scheme but not complied and there are existing programs and policies in the school but most of

them are not sustained.

To support this conclusion, Debrah, Vidal and Dinis (2020) disclosed that there is a significant relationship between teachers' and students' knowledge and attitudes towards SWM, as well as differences in awareness, attitude, and practices of SWM linked with education and age, were also found. Additionally, the research also discovered that most developing countries lack environmental education and is a contributing factor in the inadequacy of practical environmental curricula of teachers so they could easily rejoin modern-day environmental issues for sustainable development and cleaner production.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: School administrators perceived that the level of implementation of Solid Waste Management (SWM) was to a high extent, whereas teachers and students believed that SWM was only fairly implemented. This indicates a discrepancy in perceptions between school administrators and the teachers and students regarding the effectiveness of SWM implementation. To address this issue and achieve a very high level of implementation, an intensified Solid Waste Management plan has been crafted. Consequently, the following recommendations are proposed: The proposed intensified SWM plan should be implemented in the selected secondary schools. Additionally, it is recommended that the school and Local Government Units (LGUs) actively participate in the rigorous execution of SWM to ensure a very high level of implementation. Furthermore, future studies should investigate the root causes of the low-level implementation of Solid Waste Management.

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